

“Financial Statement Analysis of Janaseva Bank “

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ABSTRACT:

The financial statement of the last two year are identify, study and the project assigned to me was to study the financial health of any bank in country. I decided to choose Maharashtra’s rapidly growing over the last few year co-operative sector banks JANSEVA sahakari. Through this report I try to analyze the financial condition of the JANSEVA bank. Through this financial analysis my aim is to understand which financial factors are affecting bank and its decision making. Afterward I try and calculate the various ratios the appreciate their impact on a company’s performance over the last two years. Interpreted on the basis of banks performance. Decisions are analyzed bank has taken in past and their impact on the bank. Finally; I studied the financial statements of the bank through the ratio analysis to analyze the position of the bank in the last two years.

Keywords:Financial analysis, profitability, liquidity, returns on equity.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Financial analysis plays a very important role in every sector of company and its shareholders. To understand the financial position of the any organization to the performance monument comparing with his previous year. It will show company’s growth rate for the year and his wealth creation for his shareholders. Because of financial analysis bank has to understand the stronger and weak part of the bank and

were he wants to work in current year to improve his financial position. Financial analysis is done with the various ratio like current ratio, acid test ratio, net working capital ratio, operating expenses to revenue, total asset turnover ratio etc. it help to investors to ascertain the profitability, financial position and future prospects . Financial statements refer two statements 1) balance sheet 2) profit and loss a/c statement by analyzing the following statement management taking various decisions on the basis of financial analysis.

2. OBJECTIVE OF STUDY:

1. To find out the financial performance of the JANSEVA Bank.
2. To analyze financial statement through analytical tool and ratio analysis.
3. To study the financial policy of the JANSEVA Bank.
4. To study strengths and weaknesses of the JANSEVA Bank.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Research methodology: research methodology is the specific procedures or techniques used to identify select, process and analyze information about a topic.

Research means is the search for information. The research includes the survey, data collection.

And a methodology is an ordinary instructive method for solving problems, tasks. Methodology refers to the way in which information is found or the way something is done.

Type of Research:

Descriptive research: the term descriptive research is used to describe the characteristic of a population or situation being studied.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Financial analysis is a descriptive type of topic because of detail study of all ratios for financial analysis is required so, therefore, descriptive studies have been selected by me.

4.1. CURRENT RATIO: FORMULA: CURRENT ASSET / CURRENT LIABILITY

Particular	2018	2019
Current asset	1400,64,94,551	1582,06,29,746
Current liability	668,38,24,720	737,49,10,121
Ratio	2.09	2.14

Interpretation:

Normally expected that the current ratio should be 2:1. Which indicate that currant asset twice as compare to current liability. In both year ratio is very good in 2019 bank raise his by increasing call money it will improve the current ratio in 2019.

4.2. NET WORKING CAPITAL RATIO:

FORMULA: CURRENT ASSET – CURRENT LIABILITY

particular	2018	2019
current asset	1400,64,94,551	1582,06,29,746
Current liability	668,38,24,720	737,49,10,121
amount	732,26,69,831	844,57,19,625

Interpretation:

Net working capital is measure of a firms overall liquidity. Bank is improving as compare with last year bank have ability to meet his current obligations.

4.3. ACID TEST RATIO:

FORMULA: CASH, SHORT TERM INVESTMENT & RECEIVABLE / CURRENT LIABILITY

particular	2018	2019
Short term investment	713,29,51,746	838,11,89,261
Current liability	668,38,24,720	737,49,10,121
ratio	1.06	1.13

Interpretation:

Acid test ratio show firm has an enough short term asset to cover its immediate liability. If ratio is lower than 1 it will show that current asset are highly depending on investment.

4.4. OPERATING EXPENSES TO REVENUE

FORMULA: OPERATING EXP / OPERATING INCOME

particular	2018	2019
Operating expenses	38,22,72,479	44,30,62,198
Operating income	174,33,94,110	176,83,83,031
Ratio	21.92	25.05

Interpretation:

Ratio shows the efficiency of a bank’s management by comparing operating expenses to net sales. If ratio is higher than efficiency is lower in 2019 ratio was going higher bank should reduce operating cost.

4.5. TOTAL ASSET TURNOVER RATIO:

FORMULA: OPERATING INCOME / TOTAL ASSET * 100

particular	2018	2019
Operating income	174,33,94,110	176,83,83,031
Total asset	2144,70,55,382	2341,96,30,810
Ratio	8.12	7.55

Interpretation:

These ratio indicating banks are using all assets for generating sales. Total asset turnover ratio is more efficient when it was higher side 4 to 6 is standard position bank have very good position but it was reduce in 2019. Because of poor inventory management.

4.6. OPERATING EXPENSES TO ASSET RATIO:

FORMULA: OPERATING EXPENSES / TOTAL ASSET* 100

Particular	2018	2019
Operating expenses	38,22,72,479	44,30,62,198
Total asset	2144,70,55,382	2341,96,30,810
Ratio	1.78	1.89

Interpretation:

The expenses ratio of an asset fund is the total percentage of fund asset used for administration, management, advertisement and other expenses. Operating expenses to asset ratio should 1% per annum of total asset it will use for cover expenses in 2019 1nd 2018. It will higher In 2019 expenses increased.

4.7. TIMES INTEREST EARNED RATIO:

FORMULA: EARNINGS BEFORE INCOME TAX / INTEREST EXPANSES

Particular	2018	2019
Earnings before income tax	15,36	16,930
Interest expanses	153,67	197,42
Ratio	9.99	8.57

Interpretation:

It measures the firms or bank is having ability to make contractual interest payment. Standard ratio is always greater than 2.5. in 2019 ratio was reduce because of bank was increase his operating expenses cost it will affecting the ratio.

4.8. INVESTMENT TO DEPOSIT RATIO:

FORMULA: TOTAL INVESTMENT / TOTAL DEPOSIT

Particular	2018	2019
Total investment	65807.15	78782.83
Total deposit	179567.50	200021.98
Ratio	0.366	0.393

Interpretation:

This ratio shows that the amount of deposit which is used to investment. JANSEVA bank ratio are gradually increasing year to year it means bank is properly utilized his deposits.

4.9. RETURN ON ASSET RATIO:

NET PROFIT AFTER TAX / TOTAL ASSET* 100

particular	2018	2019
Net profit	15,36,07,645.93	12,09,19,657.84
Total asset	188,00,66,733.13	189,05,05,943.34
Ratio	8.17	6.39

Interpretation:

It will measure overall effectiveness of management in generating profit. Standard is 5 or more than 5 .it better for bank in 2019 banks profit are reduce because of that ratio was going down.

4.10. RETURN ON SHAREHOLDER’S EQUITY:

$$\text{NET PROFIT} / \text{SHAREHOLDERS EQUITY} * 100$$

Particular	2018	2019
Net profit	15,36,08,411	12,09,20,125.41
Shareholders’ equity	49,14,23,675	49,65,11,100
Ratio	31.25	24.35

Interpretation:

ROI is a measure of management ability to generate income from the equity available. Generally 15-20 is considered good. But 2019 ratio was reduce because of the profit of the bank goes down it was main problem.

4.11. SWOT ANALYSIS:

Strengths:

- Large customer base.
- Strong capital.
- Bank is financially safe.
- Community involvement.
- Goodwill of bank is very good.
- Bank has huge amount of deposit.

Weakness:

- Lack of technological resources like computerized banking.
- Manual service costly.
- Lack of promotional activity.
- Incentive system is very weak than private bank.

Opportunities:

- Increasing retail banking.
- Bank has many branches in local area so it can easily expand its activity.
- Bank can attract the people by offering new schemes.

Threats:

- Political instability.
- Continuous increasing non banking competitor offering similar services.
- Government facility is insufficient when economic condition of country becomes unfavorable.

5.FINDINGS:

1. Current ratio of bank increasing in 2019 it means bank has ability to meet current liability.
2. Current ratio was improved because of short term loans collected by bank.
3. Operating cost of bank is too high. To reduce it bank has to embrace technology.
4. Total asset turnover ratio is reduced in 2019 because of reduction of profit of bank and bad asset management.
5. Operating expenses to asset ratio was increased it shows that company has high operating expenses.
6. Return on shareholder equity went down 31.25 % to 24.35 % in 2019 bank has to improve.

6. SUGGESTIONS:

1. Acid test ratio shows too much higher side it shows current assets depending on inventory to reduce it.
2. Operating expenses bank has to reduce because of those operating expenses to revenue it was increased in 2019.
3. Total asset turnover ratio was reduced in 2019 because of poor inventory management they have to improve it.

4. Total fund of asset are used for operating expenses are higher side bank has to reduce it.
5. Investment to deposit ratio is improving year to year his also bank have chance to improve as compare with other banks it was not up to the mark.
6. Bank has to improve his profit it was affecting by unsecured loan and advances return on shareholders' equity it was reduce.

7. CONCLUSION:

If you want to understand company's financial health that time use financial analysis. JANSEVA bank is one of the most growing bank in Maharashtra state. Bank have good scoop for development in his sector. Bank has to improve his asset management and technological development. Bank is co-operative bank because of that they will work on his local operational area to improve deposit in to bank it will give long term and loyal customers to bank. Analysis was revels that no difference between deposit, investment, borrowing, advances etc. bank has to be finding out remedy on reduction in profit level.

8. REFERENCES:

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